

**ACTUAL ISSUES OF WORKING WITH ASSIGNMENTS
IN PHILOLOGICAL SUBJECTS IN HIGHER
EDUCATION****Ozoda Khazratkulova**

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nafisbekmamatova21@gmail.com<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18017367>**ARTICLE INFO**Received: 20th December 2025Accepted: 21st December 2025Online: 22nd December 2025**KEYWORDS***skills-building tasks and exercises, higher education, philology, educational tasks, independent learning tasks, textbooks and manuals.***ABSTRACT**

The use of learning tasks in teaching the Uzbek language, including linguistics, is also a serious problem. After all, communication between the teacher and the student mainly occurs through learning tasks. It should be noted that in the teaching of language teaching methods and linguistics, special attention is not paid to improving learning tasks. In particular, textbooks and study guides use traditional questions and tasks.

There have also been some studies on the issue of the essential distinction between the terms “exercise” and “task” in education. In particular, in the educational materials of the methodologist-scientist M. Saidov, he divides educational tasks into three types, distinguishes them from each other, and emphasizes that teachers often confuse the concepts of “exercise”, “task” and “issue” in the course of their work. The scientist agrees with the opinion of Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences A. Gulyamov that “Exercise is both a form of an educational task and a specific method of teaching,” and recognizes that the task is a part of the exercise, it is mainly expressed in the conditions of the exercise, and the task represents a narrower concept than the exercise.¹

As is known, in language textbooks, the terms "exercise", "question" and "task" are mainly used, and in natural and exact sciences, the term "masale" is used. All of them are types of work that fall under the category of educational tasks, and this term is also interpreted as educational tasks in some studies.²

As we have noted above, the main goal and task of language education stems from the content and functional differentiation of learning tasks. Therefore, in our research work, it is necessary to separately address the issue of the content, use, functions and classification of

1 Саидов М. Ўзбек мактабларининг 5-синфларида она тили таълими жараёнида тафаккурни ривожлантирувчи ўқув топшириқлари ва улардан фойдаланиш методикаси: пед. фан. ном-ди дисс. автореф.ТДПУ. –Тошкент, 2000. – 25 б.

2 Қўчқорова Ф. М. Янги авлод дарсликлариди тақдим этиладиган ўқув материалларини концентризми принципи асосида структуралашнинг дидактик параметрлари: фалсафа фан. докт. ... дисс.(PhD). – Тошкент, 2018. –13-бет.

the terms "exercise", "question", "task".

G. Hamroev emphasizes that the assignment is a basic educational task that includes both an exercise and a question, directs the student to acquire knowledge, participates in assessment, and organizes the formation of skills through exercises based on repetition. Based on long-term observations and analyses, it can be concluded that the so-called exercises in the "Mother Tongue" textbooks are not exercises at all, that is, they do not meet the requirements of an exercise. In fact, an exercise is not a means of imparting knowledge, it should be used to develop skills and competencies. An assignment is used to acquire knowledge, organize training, and evaluate acquired knowledge and skills; a question is used to encourage the student to think and test. In practice, they are used in combination. For this reason, even though methods and textbook content are updated, the effectiveness of lessons does not increase significantly, and speech skills do not fully develop. In this sense, learning tasks are of great importance in revealing the content of native language learning and developing speech skills, and special attention is required to create and use learning tasks in the educational process.

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T/r	The content of teaching tasks used in practice in higher philological education	Proposed pragmatic learning tasks
1.	What are the historical roots of the current Uzbek literary language?	What are the ancient sources that are closest phonetically and lexically to the current Uzbek literary language? Give examples to support your opinion.
2.	What is your opinion about the relationship between the subject "Methodology of Teaching the Uzbek Language" and other subjects?	What is the relationship between the discipline of Uzbek language teaching methodology and the discipline of child psychology? Explain the relationship between the disciplines with examples.
3.	Who is responsible for leading the activities of the Methodological Association?	How can we organize the development of teaching methods in schools? Prepare proposals.

In higher philological education, especially in the areas of Uzbek language and literature, assignments and questions are mainly used. They do not contain exercises, which is why the shortcomings in the oral and written speech of future philologists, teachers of the native language and literature are not eliminated, but are added to the educational process, production, and have a negative impact on the literacy of students and those around them.

The textbook "Current Uzbek Literary Language" by H. Jamolkhonov provides the following learning tasks to reinforce the topic:

Review questions

1. What are the historical roots of the current Uzbek literary language?
2. What is the practical significance of being aware of such historical roots and processes?
3. What vowels did the ancient Uzbek language consist of?
4. What do you know about the vocalism of the Old Turkic and Old Uzbek literary

languages?

5. How do you understand contrast pairs in the vocalism system?

6. How many vowels are there in the vocalism of the current Uzbek literary language?

Do they form contrasting pairs according to the sign of thickness and thinness?

7. What consonants did the consonantism of the Old Turkic language consist of? What about the consonantism of the Old Uzbek literary language?

8. What are the main differences between the consonant system of the current Uzbek literary language and the ancient Turkic language?

9. What changes have occurred in the paradigmatic and syntagmatic properties of phonemes during the historical development from the ancient Turkic language to the current Uzbek literary language?

10. What do you know about synharmonism? Is there synharmonism in the current Uzbek literary language? What about dialects?

11. What changes occurred in the lexical level (vocabulary richness) of the language during the period from the ancient Turkic language to the current Uzbek literary language?

12. What do you know about changes in the grammatical structure of a language?

13. What are your thoughts on the dialectal foundations of the current Uzbek literary language?

14. What are the dialects of the Uzbek language combined into?

15. What sections are there in the course "Modern Uzbek Literary Language"?³

These questions serve to provide students with knowledge or to test their understanding of the subject. In fact, it is advisable to provide not only questions in the textbook, but also assignments and, where necessary, exercises.

In recent years, another problem has arisen in this regard. The subject "Modern Uzbek literary language" has been included in the curriculum of both the faculties of philology and the faculties of Uzbek language and literature. However, even though they are two different specializations, the topics covered in the program are the same, that is, lexeme, phraseme, phoneme, semantic field, and other similar highly scientific topics. Future philologists need these topics and concepts, but it is not in line with pragmatic principles for school teachers to have such in-depth knowledge, in our opinion.

The textbook "Methodology of Teaching the Uzbek Language", published for philology faculties of universities and pedagogical institutes, contains the following questions and assignments: What do you know about the formation, development, and current status of "Methodology of Teaching the Uzbek Language" as a discipline? How many periods can the formation of the discipline "Methodology of Teaching the Uzbek Language" be divided into? What do you understand by "explanatory teaching" education? What do you know about the socio-political, cultural and educational changes that occurred in Turkestan at the beginning of the 20th century? What was the basis for the creation of textbooks in a new direction from "Mother Language"? Whose scientific views and works were of great importance in the development of the discipline of Uzbek language teaching methodology in the 50s–80s? Talk about the reforms in the field of native language education during the years of independence? Justify the object, subject, goals and objectives of the discipline "Methodology of Uzbek

³Jamolxonov H. Hozirgi o'zbek adabiy tili. Darslik. –Toshkent. Talqin. 2005, 260 b.

language teaching". What do you understand by the system of necessary knowledge, skills and abilities in the native language? Name and justify the scientific research methods of the subject "Methodology of teaching the Uzbek language". Tell us about diagnostic analysis and its stages. What is your opinion about the relationship of the subject "Methodology of teaching the Uzbek language" with other subjects? What do you understand by the term "creativity" and "creativity" of a teacher? What are the tasks of the school's native language methodological association? What work is done with young teachers? How is the native language classroom equipped at school? What should a native language teacher follow when drawing up a progressive work plan? What is the importance of creating an educational and methodological complex in the subject of the native language at school? Who is responsible for leading the activities of the methodological association? How many times a year and when are meetings of the methodological association held?⁴

This textbook is designed based on the established requirements, but it is advisable to create pragmatic tasks that teach the content of the educational tasks in it, and direct the student to think and reflect. The question in the textbook, "Tell me about the reforms in the field of mother tongue education during the years of independence?" the assignment is considered an assignment even though it has a question mark, but it does not encourage the student to think. Or the assignment "Justify the object, subject, goals and objectives of the subject "Methodology of Teaching the Uzbek Language" only encourages the student to refer to the appropriate page in the textbook. In our opinion, textbooks should contain assignments and creative questions that direct the student to a separate research on the topic.

In conclusion, it can be said that in order for students in higher philological education to become qualified specialists in their fields, it is necessary to improve the content of questions and assignments in textbooks, including in class exercises. Otherwise, the student may not be able to acquire the necessary skills and qualifications in the specialty and may not find his place in society. Educational tasks can be said to be the fulcrum of education, and during classes, the tasks can direct the student in any direction. If teaching linguistics subjects is not limited to questions alone, but also includes assignments and exercises where possible, the quality of education can increase.

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